

studies of the photo-oxidation of monohydric alcohols by the uranyl ions^{7,8} and other metal ions⁹⁻¹². One is the hydrogen atom abstraction producing a carbon-centered hydroxyalkyl radical (equation 2) and the other the electron transfer reaction producing an oxygen-centered alkoxy radical (equations 3 and 4).

H-abstraction :

Electron transfer :

The results (Table 1 and Fig. 1) indicate that the evidence of spin-trapping of the carbon-centered radicals by the spin-trap (equation 5) supports the mechanism (equation 2) for the title reaction under the present experimental conditions.

where, R is the remaining part of the diol/triol/alditol molecule.

The hydrogen abstraction mechanism (equation 2) and the trapping of carbon-centered free radicals in these reactions are further supported by the matrix isolation experiment performed at 77 K using liquid nitrogen. The resulting esr spectrum obtained on the photolysis of uranyl nitrate (1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) in ethane-1,2-diol gave a familiar recognisable triplet ($a_H = 1.98$ mT) due to $\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}.\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ consistent with the earlier report¹⁴.

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Synthesis and Pharmacological Studies of 2-N-Ethyl-3,4-naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan

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DETAILED studies of 6,7-benzomorphan¹, the potent analgesics with minor toxic effects², have resulted in the synthesis of various related compounds for the first time in our laboratory³. The modification of piperidine ring of 6,7-benzomorphan to benzo[*f*]tetrahydroquinoline system has resulted in 3,4-naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan which are of potential analgesic interest, 2-N-methyl-3,4-naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan is found to be toxic (ALD₅₀ = 273 mg/kg i.p.) with a significant analgesic ($P < 0.001$) and CNS depressant activity ($P < 0.001$).

The present communication deals with⁴ the synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of 2-N-ethyl-3,4-naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan (2) HCl. The structure was established by elemental analysis, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data.

In the ¹H nmr spectrum of 2.HCl (C₂₂H₂₁N.HCl), signals at δ 4.75 (2H, q) and 1.0 (3H, t) indicated the presence of N-ethyl group. Signals at δ 3.25 (2H, t) and 4.0 (2H, d) respectively accounted for methylene protons at C-8 and C-9. Signals at

δ 4.9 (1H, t) and 2.5 (1H, m) established the presence of protons at C-5 and C-1 respectively. A complicated pattern in the range δ 6.8–8.8 (7.5) showed the presence of ten aromatic protons. The mass spectrum of 2 gave a molecular ion peak at M^+ 300. Other characteristic peaks were obtained at m/z 299, 284, 270, 269, 268, 254, 253, 239, 208, 179, 157 and 36 (base peak).

2.HCl (in a solution of propylene glycol) was subjected to preliminary pharmacological screening on albino mice (15–20 g) of either sex. Its LD_{50} value was 316.24 mg/kg i.p., with significant CNS depressant activity.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected 1H nmr spectrum was recorded on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer and mass spectrum on a Hitachi-RMu-6EL spectrometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel-G and benzene–ethanol–ammonia (7 : 2 : 1, v/v).

2-Benzyl-1-ethyl-1,2-dihydro-benzo[f]quinoline (1) : Freshly prepared benzylmagnesium chloride (7.56 g benzyl chloride and 1.44 g magnesium) was slowly added to benzo[f]quinolinium ethiodide (13.4 g) with continuous stirring for 3 h at 40–50°. After refluxing, the mixture was poured onto crushed ice (100 g) containing NH_4Cl (10 g) and concentrated HCl (10 ml). It was then basified with NH_4OH and extracted with ether (250 ml). The ether extract was dehydrated (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated to afford an oil which on distillation at 160° (0.2 mm) gave 1 (3.22 g, 27%); 1.HCl, m.p. 205° (Found: N, 4.48. $C_{21}H_{21}N.HCl$ requires: N, 4.32%); recrystallised from acetone–petroleum ether (1 : 4).

2-N-Ethyl-(3,4-a)naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan (2) : A mixture of 1 (3.6 g) and 85% H_3PO_4 (30 ml) was refluxed for 48 h at 140°. It was then poured onto crushed ice (100 g) basified with NH_4OH and extracted with ether (250 ml). Concentration of the ethereal layer afforded an oil which was distilled at 180° (0.2 mm) to give 2 (1.50 g, 42%); 2.HCl m.p. 125° (Found: C, 77.80; H, 6.92. $C_{21}H_{21}N.HCl$ requires: C, 77.59; H, 6.80).

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Synthesis of Indeno[2,1-c]isocoumarins and Indeno[2,1-c]isoquinolones. Part-II

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THE indenoisocoumarins have an unsaturated β -lactone ring in the isocoumarin moiety and hence may be expected to exhibit physiological properties. Chatterjea and Mukherjee^{1,2} reported the synthesis of a few indenoisocoumarins (5) by heating α -benzylhomophthalic acids (2) with commercial PPA. Compounds 2 in turn were obtained by the interaction of benzaldehydes with dimethyl homophthalate in the presence of sodium methoxide followed by saponification of the resulting product and subsequent sodium amalgam reduction of α -benzylidene homophthalic acids (1). In an alternative route these authors¹ carried out the Stobbe condensation of *o*-carboxybenzaldehydes with diethyl homophthalates followed by reduction of the resulting *o*-carboxy- α -benzylidenehomophthalic acid (3) as usual to *o*-carboxy- α -benzylhomophthalic acids (4), which when heated with Ac_2O gave indeno[1,2-c]isocoumarins (5). These syntheses involve a number of steps and consequently the yield of indenoisocoumarins was always low.

